

Precision Agriculture: Spotting and Spraying Yellow Defected Plant

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Abstract— The agricultural sector plays an important role in the process of economic development of a country. The conventional pesticide spraying method involves uniform spraying of the entire field even when only some plants are infected. This results in pesticide wastage, increased operation costs, and health hazards. Hence, there is a strong need for an automated, precise, and selective spraying of the plants. This project presents a Precision Agriculture System using Drone Technology for Spotting and Spraying Yellow Defected Plants. The proposed system will consist of a quadcopter with a high-resolution camera and an image processing tool. The captured image is processed and compared with various examples, and the suitable control signal is given to the spraying mechanism for the spraying of the defected plant. This selective spraying reduces the waste of pesticides and decreases the environmental impact while ensuring proper care of the plants. This system integrates the Robot Operating System (ROS) for the control and communication, while the OpenCV enable the real time image processing of the defective plant. The drone mechanical build includes with light weight carbon fibre body with high resolution camera and 3D printed custom parts for delicate electronics. Together these components ensure accurate detection and spraying of the defected plants. The proposed system offers several advantages such as reduced chemical usage, improved crop yield, lower labour requirements, and enhanced farming efficiency. The future

work will focus on the integration of the advanced machine learning models to accurately find the defected plant and enhancing autonomous path planning through ROS for optimized field coverage. This project contributes toward the development of sustainable and intelligent farming solutions in modern precision agriculture.

Keywords--- Agriculture, Drone, ROS, OpenCV, Fusion 360

I. INTRODUCTION

The India's GDP exceeds \$4 trillion level, estimated around \$4.5 trillion level in which agriculture contributes around 16% to 18% as of 2023-24. Agriculture has major problems which includes water scarcity, climatic change which majorly include pest and disease attacks, we are here are to resolve the pest problems. In the early days farmers used natural and traditional methods like burned wood(ash), smoke method (burned dry leaves, cow dunk, crop rotation) to control the pest without chemicals. Now a days farmers use chemical pesticides quickly to kill the harmful insects and to increase crop yield and to reduce the post-harvest loss (stored grains from insect). The most commonly used way of spraying pesticides by farmers is knapsack sprayer method (the pesticides liquid is pumped manually using a lever, it sprays through a nozzle on to the crop). To reduce the human need in the field and to reduce the time consumption we use agriculture drones. Our project is to reduce the

consumption of the pesticides and to spot the mentioned (yellow) defected plants by spotting each plant separately through autonomous methods.

II. STATE OF THE ART

AI Tools and Autonomous precision Techniques to spray only the defected plants. In this we use AI tools, sensors and the Precision Techniques to spray the pesticides to only the defected plants and flowers.

A. Plant Disease Detection

For the appropriate evaluation of the crop farmers use the phytosanitary method (checking the presence and spread of plant disease). This method seems useful for the farmers to calculate timely estimation of disease incidence, symptoms severity and it help them decide the correct time to take actions such as spraying pesticides. Disease detection is divided into two types direct and indirect method. Direct methods are known as Traditional Method such as observing visible plants symptoms and in Laboratories they use Polymerase method to identify the pest attack on the plants through Microscope. With help of these methods diseases are identified accurately, but they are slow, time-consuming and required lab facilities, so they are not suitable for quick detection.

Smart Agriculture, also known as Precision Agriculture or Smart Farming. In which it utilizes advanced technologies to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of agriculture. In this system we integrate the Information and Communication Technology with the Traditional Farming Techniques to enhance the crop production and to reduce the wastage (water and pesticides) to minimize the environmental impacts. IOT plays a vital role in Smart Agriculture through sensors by enabling farmers to track and monitor farming system. These sensors can be used for various purposes such as soil moisture monitoring, water tank level monitoring, equipment tracking and etc.

B. Smart Spraying

Spraying is the successful method to apply pesticides, fertilizers and nutrients to the plants. Mostly followed method is Knapsack method, which we can spray evenly on the plant. Which may lead to wastage of water and pesticides. To avoid these wastages, we integrate AI and automation to spray chemicals only where we needed. This process is known as Smart Spraying. In this type of spraying system drones will detect the defect autonomously and spray the defected plants

C. Image Processing

In a field of Computer Vision and Digital Signal Processing the Image Processing is done. This method is used to capture the image via high resolution camera [image Acquisition]. Where the captured image is pre-processed (noise removal, resizing, filtering). Image processing helps farmers analyse crops using images instead of manual inspection and Detect diseases, pests, and nutrient deficiencies and in Drone-Based Monitoring drones capture field images and analyse large farms quickly.

III SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Overall Architecture

The overall architecture and methodology of the smart agriculture system are designed to combine image capture, processing, and automated decision-making into a single working model. In this system, a camera mounted on the drone is used to capture real-time images of the crops while flying over the field. These images are then sent to the onboard processing unit, the Radxa 4D, where basic pre-processing steps like noise removal and resizing are performed to improve clarity. After that, image processing is carried out using OpenCV, where the system analyses the images to identify unhealthy plants based on visible features such as colour changes, especially the yellowing of leaves. The processed results are then checked using a simple decision-making logic to determine whether the plant is affected or not. If the level of infection crosses predefined

threshold, a control signal is generated and sent to the motor driver through GPIO or UART communication. This activates the spraying system, which includes a pump and nozzle, to spray pesticides only on the affected plants. If no issue is detected, the drone continues scanning the field. This approach helps in reducing manual work, saving chemicals, and improving overall efficiency in crop monitoring and treatment.

B. Hardware Components Used

Camera: Radxa Camera 4K IMX415 The Radxa Camera 4K IMX415 (**FIGURE:1**) is an 8-megapixel camera capable of capturing high-resolution images up to 4K (3840×2160 pixels), providing clear with detailed visual data for analysis. It also supports lower resolutions such as 1080p (1920×1080) and 720p (1280×720), which can be used for faster processing and real-time applications. The camera can record video at up to 30 frames per second at 4K resolution, making it suitable for continuous monitoring.

FIGURE:1

4-in-1 ESC (55A) The Electronic Speed Controller (ESC) (**FIGURE:1.1**) is responsible for controlling the speed of the BLDC motors. A 4-in-1 ESC means a single unit controls four motors, reducing wiring complexity and weight. It takes low-power signals from the flight controller and converts them into high-power signals required to drive the motors. The 55A rating indicates it can handle high current, which is important for heavy-lift drones.

3D Printer In this project, 3D printing technology is used to design and fabricate custom components such as the canopy, battery holder, tank, and Radxa holder. Using materials like PETG, these parts are printed to be lightweight, strong, and suitable for drone applications.

FIGURE:1.1

The canopy helps protect internal electronics from dust and external damage, while the battery holder ensures the battery is securely fixed during flight. The tank is designed to store the spraying liquid efficiently without leakage, and the Radxa holder provides proper mounting and stability for the Radxa 4D. By using 3D printing, the design can be easily customized according to the drone structure, reducing weight and improving overall system integration.

Flysky FS-i6S Transmitter This is the remote control used by the operator to manually control the drone. It sends signals to the flight controller for basic movements like throttle, pitch, roll, and yaw. It is useful for manual operation and safety control.

Flight Controller (MicoAir405v2) The flight controller is the main brain of the drone that controls its overall movement and stability. It continuously receives data from sensors like accelerometer and adjusts the speed of each motor to keep the drone balanced. It also

processes commands from the remote controller and ensures smooth take off, landing, and navigation. In this project, it plays a key role in maintaining stable flight while carrying additional load like camera and spraying system.

ESP32-C3 (Telemetry Module) The ESP32-C3 is used in this project (shown in **FIGURE:1.2**) as a telemetry module to enable wireless communication between the drone and the ground system. It helps in sending real-time data such as system status, sensor readings, and detection results.

FIGURE:1.2

RADXA ROCK 4D (shown in **FIGURE:1.3**) In our project, the Radxa ROCK 4D acts as the main processing unit (brain) of the system. It receives real-time images from the Radxa

FIGURE:1.3

Camera 4K IMX415 mounted on the drone. Once the image is captured, it is sent to the Radxa board where image processing is performed using OpenCV. The processing node uses OpenCV to analyse the images. It performs steps like resizing, noise removal, and colour conversion to HSV. The system then detects yellow regions in the leaves, which indicate disease or nutrient deficiency. After detection, the affected area is calculated and compared with a predefined threshold value, by using ROS2 on the Radxa ROCK 4D, the system becomes modular and well-organized, allowing efficient communication between components and enabling real-time operation. This integration ensures accurate detection, automated response, and improved efficiency in precision agriculture applications.

C. ROS2-Based System Architecture

The ROS2-based system architecture for autonomous control is implemented on the Radxa ROCK 4D, which acts as the central processing unit of the drone. Using ROS 2, the system is divided into multiple nodes that handle different tasks such as image acquisition, processing, decision-making, and control. A camera node captures real-time images from the Radxa Camera 4K IMX415 and publishes them

to a topic. These images are received by a processing node, where they are analyzed using OpenCV and optional AI models to detect diseased plants. The results are then published to another topic, which is accessed by a decision node to determine whether action is required. Based on this decision, control commands are generated and sent to the flight controller for navigation adjustments and to the actuation system for spraying. A separate control node manages the pump and nozzle by sending signals through GPIO or UART. Additionally, telemetry data can be transmitted using communication modules for monitoring purposes. This ROS2-based architecture enables modular design, real-time communication, and easy integration of different system components, making the drone capable of autonomous operation in precision agriculture.

The results are then sent to a decision node, which checks whether the detected condition exceeds a predefined threshold. If a diseased plant is identified, a control command is generated and published to a control topic. A control node receives this command and sends signals through GPIO or UART to activate the spraying mechanism. If no issue is detected, the system continues scanning. The use of Gazebo simulation and virtual environment (shown in **FIGURE:2** and **FIGURE:2.1**) helps in testing algorithms, validating system performance, and reducing risks before implementing the system on the actual drone. This approach ensures a reliable, flexible, and efficient precision agriculture system.

FIGURE:2

FIGURE:2.1

D. Usage of OpenCV

In this project, OpenCV is used along with AI-based techniques to perform accurate plant disease detection. Initially, images are captured using the Radxa Camera 4K IMX415 and processed on the Radxa ROCK 4D. OpenCV is used for basic image processing tasks such as resizing, noise removal, and converting images from RGB to HSV colour space. It also helps in detecting colour variations like yellowing of leaves and calculating the affected area using thresholding methods.

To improve detection accuracy, a deep learning model based on YOLOv8 is used. This model is trained using a dataset of plant images that include both healthy and diseased samples. During the training process, the neural network learns important features such as colour patterns, texture, and shape of leaves. The trained model is then converted into an optimized format (such as RKNN) and deployed on the system for real-time inference. When the drone captures images, the model processes them and provides outputs

like bounding boxes, class labels, and confidence scores for detected diseased plants.

The results from both OpenCV and the trained AI model are combined to make a final decision. If the detected disease level exceeds a predefined threshold, a control signal is generated to activate the spraying mechanism. This combination of traditional image processing and trained neural network models ensures higher accuracy, better detection capability, and efficient operation of the smart agriculture system.

HSV-Based Yellow Leaf Detection Using OpenCV

The entire implementation was developed and executed using PyCharm, which provides an efficient environment for writing, debugging, and running Python programs. The system processes a video input containing plant images. First, the video frame is converted from BGR colour space to HSV color space. HSV is preferred because it separates color information (Hue) from brightness (Value), making color detection more reliable under different lighting conditions.

Trackbars are created to adjust the HSV values dynamically. These sliders allow the user to set minimum and maximum ranges for Hue, Saturation, and Value in real time. The selected HSV range is used to generate a binary mask where the target colour (yellow leaves) appears in white and all other regions appear in black.

To reduce noise and improve detection accuracy, morphological operations such as opening and closing are applied using a kernel. After this, contour detection is performed to identify the boundaries of the detected regions. Small contours that fall below a minimum area threshold are ignored to eliminate unwanted noise.

All valid contour points are merged, and a single bounding rectangle is drawn around the detected yellow regions. The system also calculates the total area of the detected region and displays the

number of contours detected (shown in **FIGURE:3**)

FIGURE:3

E. Fusion 360 (Designing using 3D printer)

The canopy of the drone (shown in **FIGURE:4.1**) is designed to protect sensitive electronic components such as the flight controller and communication modules from external conditions like dust and moisture. Its streamlined shape helps in reducing air resistance during flight, while the provided ventilation holes allow proper heat dissipation to prevent overheating. At the same time, the lightweight design ensures that it does not affect the payload capacity or overall flight efficiency. The GPS holder is positioned at a higher location above the main frame to improve signal reception and reduce interference from other electronic components, and it is designed with sufficient rigidity to maintain stability during flight.

The pesticide tank mount plays a crucial role in maintaining the drone's balance during spraying operations. It is placed at the centre of the frame to ensure proper centre of gravity, which is essential for stable flight. The mount is designed to be strong and secure, with a locking mechanism to prevent movement during

operation, and it is capable of handling the dynamic forces caused by the liquid.

FIGURE:4

inside the tank. Similarly, the battery holder is designed to safely hold high-capacity Li-Po batteries. It includes a firm grip to prevent displacement, along with features to absorb vibrations and mechanical stress. Proper ventilation is also provided to avoid overheating, and the arrangement of the batteries ensures even weight distribution for better flight performance.

All these structural components are manufactured using PETG HF filament through 3D printing. This material is chosen due to its high strength, durability, and resistance to heat and impact. Compared to materials like PLA, PETG is more suitable for outdoor drone applications, making it ideal for components such as the canopy, tank mount, and battery holder.

FIGURE:4.1

Using materials like PETG filament, the 3D printer builds each part layer by layer with high precision. This method allows easy customization of components based on the drone's design requirements. It also helps in reducing weight, improving strength, and ensuring proper fitting of all parts. Overall, 3D printing provides a cost-effective and flexible solution for developing durable and lightweight structures for the drone.

F. Experimental Setup

Field Setup The experimental setup was carried out in an agricultural field where the drone was tested under real-time conditions. The drone was equipped with all necessary components including the Radxa Camera 4K IMX415, spraying system, and processing unit Radxa ROCK 4D. The field area was selected to include both healthy and diseased plants to properly evaluate the system performance. The drone was calibrated and positioned to fly at needed altitude to capture clear images of the crops.

Data Collection During the experiment, images of crops were captured continuously using the onboard camera. These images were processed using OpenCV and AI models such as YOLOv8. The collected data included images of both healthy and diseased plants, along with detection results such as affected area, classification output, and spray activation status. This data was also used for training and testing the model to improve detection accuracy.

Testing Condition The system was tested under different environmental conditions to evaluate its performance (shown in **FIGURE:5**). These included variations in lighting (morning and afternoon), different plant densities, and varying levels of disease severity. The drone was tested at different heights and speeds to ensure proper image capture and detection accuracy.

FIGURE:5

The performance was evaluated based on parameters such as detection accuracy, response time, and effectiveness of targeted spraying. These tests helped in verifying the reliability and efficiency of the system in real-world agricultural conditions.

G. Results and Discussion

Detection Accuracy Detection accuracy refers to how correctly the system identifies diseased and healthy plants. It measures the performance of the image processing and AI model used in the system.

In this project, detection accuracy is evaluated based on the results obtained from OpenCV and the AI model YOLOv8. The system compares the predicted results (detected plants) with the actual condition of the plants in the field.

Spraying efficiency Spraying efficiency refers to how effectively the drone delivers the pesticide, herbicide, or nutrient solution to the target crops while minimizing wastage and off-target drift. In this experiment, efficiency was evaluated based on several parameters: Target accuracy, coverage uniformity, reduction wastage.

H. Advantage of the System

Real-Time Image Processing (OpenCV) – OpenCV allows the drone to process high-resolution images captured by the Radxa Camera 4K IMX415 in real-time, enabling immediate detection of diseased plants and precise spraying.
Advanced Object Detection (AI Integration) – Combined with AI models like YOLOv8, OpenCV helps identify plant health conditions

accurately, segment affected areas, and provide actionable insights for targeted spraying.

Modular and Scalable Robotics Framework (ROS2) – ROS2 provides a robust communication and control framework for the drone, making it easier to integrate sensors, cameras, and spraying mechanisms. It allows different components (flight controller, AI module, spraying system) to work in coordination efficiently.

Real-Time Decision Making – ROS2's publisher-subscriber model enables real-time transmission of sensor and camera data, allowing the drone to make immediate decisions about which areas to spray.

Simulation and Testing Capabilities– ROS2 supports simulation environments where drone behaviour can be tested virtually before deployment, reducing risks and optimizing flight paths for efficiency.

Improved Automation – Together, OpenCV and ROS2 enable a fully automated system for crop monitoring and spraying, reducing the need for human intervention and enhancing operational efficiency.

Flexibility and Extensibility – New sensors, AI models, or spraying patterns can be integrated into the system with minimal changes, making the project adaptable for various crops and agricultural needs.

Data Logging and Analysis – ROS2 allows structured data collection from sensors and spraying actions, while OpenCV can analyse image-based outcomes, providing a feedback loop to improve spraying accuracy and efficiency over time.

I. LIMITATIONS

1. **Lighting Condition Issues** – The performance of the camera and image processing can be affected by varying light conditions, such as shadows, bright sunlight, or cloudy weather, which may reduce detection accuracy.
2. **Camera Accuracy** – Although the Radxa Camera 4K IMX415 provides high-resolution images, limitations in camera resolution, lens

quality, or field-of-view can affect the precision of plant detection and spraying coverage.

Environmental Factors– Wind, rain, or uneven terrain can impact drone stability, spray drift, and overall system efficiency.

System Complexity–Integration of OpenCV, ROS2, AI models, and hardware components requires technical expertise for calibration, maintenance and troubleshooting

J. FUTURE SCOPE

Integration with Multi-Spectral and Thermal Cameras – Using additional sensors like multi-spectral or thermal cameras can improve early detection of crop stress, nutrient deficiencies, and disease outbreaks.

Expansion to Multiple Crop Types – By training AI models on diverse crops, the system can be adapted for use across different agricultural fields, improving versatility and scalability.

Real-Time Data Analytics and Cloud Integration – Integrating the drone system with cloud platforms can allow large-scale data collection, remote monitoring, and predictive analysis for better crop management.

Swarm Drone Technology – Deploying multiple drones in coordination can reduce spraying time for large fields and increase operational efficiency.

Environmental and Sustainability Metrics – Future versions could include real-time monitoring of environmental impact, chemical usage efficiency, and soil health to promote sustainable farming practices.

Integration with IoT and Smart Farming Platforms – Connecting the drone system to IoT networks and farm management platforms can allow fully automated, data-driven agricultural practices.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates the development and implementation of an AI-powered drone system for precision agriculture, integrating OpenCV,

ROS2, YOLOv8, and an automated spraying mechanism. The experimental setup validated the system's ability to detect diseased plants accurately and spray targeted areas efficiently, reducing chemical usage and minimizing environmental impact.

The project has a significant impact on precision agriculture by enabling real-time crop monitoring, early disease detection, and data-driven decision-making. By automating labour-intensive tasks and improving spraying accuracy, the system contributes to higher crop health, better yields, and sustainable farming practices.

For farmers, the system offers tangible benefits, including reduced labour costs, optimized use of agrochemicals, improved crop quality, and enhanced operational efficiency. The integration of AI and robotics in agriculture thus represents a step forward in creating smart, sustainable, and cost-effective farming solutions.

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